

SPEECH DEVELOPMENT IN PRIMARY SCHOOL AGE

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7734116>

ELSEVIER

Received: 12-03-2023

Accepted: 13-03-2023

Published: 22-03-2023

Dedakhanov Abdumalik Mutallievich.

Independent applicant of Namangan State University

Abstract: This article discusses the development of speech in primary school age, its complex aspects, getting rid of dialectisms, developing perseverance, attentiveness, and thinking of a younger student.

Keywords: thinking, mindfulness, speech development, oral, written speech

About: FARS Publishers has been established with the aim of spreading quality scientific information to the research community throughout the universe. Open Access process eliminates the barriers associated with the older publication models, thus matching up with the rapidity of the twenty-first century.

For the development of speech in primary school age, it is necessary to take into account many aspects of the formation of a younger student. This is a complex and multidimensional process. First of all, the improvement of oral speech: improving the purity of sound pronunciation, getting rid of dialectisms, mastering complex grammatical structures, the use of adverbial phrases, passive voice, etc.

The circle of communication and the scope of oral speech are expanding. The model is the competent and rich speech of the teacher. Coming to the 1st grade and joining the complex process of schooling, many other requirements are imposed on him.

To do this, a younger student needs to develop perseverance, attentiveness, be able to catch the main thing from the context of the teacher, and new, written, complex types of speech appear: reading and writing. These are the most important achievements of the student, based on the mechanisms of encoding sounds and decoding graphemes. These are forms of symbolic communication. They suggest a new level of perception, attention, memory, associations with existing knowledge. Only under these conditions, reading will be the perception of the meaning of the text, and writing will be the transmission of meaning.

Mastering symbolic communication begins with understanding the child's speech, listening to stories and "reading" from memory texts in a favorite book or inscriptions in a familiar situation. By reading familiar names and names, the child can learn to read by himself, which is quite common these days. Such self-study

served as the basis for the theory of internal spontaneous language maturation, which supposedly "suddenly" brings literacy to the surface.⁵⁴

The scientific explanation of such facts is given by L. S. Vygotsky's theory about the "zone of immediate development" of a child during interaction with literate people, about the meaning of an enriched environment. The components of such an environment are adults reading, books at the disposal of the child, adult stories and listening to children's stories, explanations of words, communication with friends, word games, interesting impressions and experiences of talking about them, playing them, and then describing them, encouraging interest in the written form of the word.

The main condition for the development of literacy is informative reading and informative writing. In the joint reading of interesting books (a line - an adult, a line - a child), first-graders are more likely to master reading than when "working out" small texts to complete memorization. For the development of writing, they suggest composing and writing fairy tales, writing letters to the teacher about events during the holidays, writing about their friends, etc. Even if part of the text is represented by a drawing, the student perceives as the main thing - the meaning of the letter, and not the image of letters and words.

It should be noted that children who have mastered reading on their own very often remain deaf to grammar. Their attention is focused on the content of the text, they recognize words by their general appearance and do not notice the peculiarities of their writing. D. B. Elkonin in his work "How to teach children to read" (1978) emphasizes the role of sound analysis of words when chips are used instead of letters, a symbolic representation of sound characteristics. Vowel, soft consonant or hard consonant - each has its own color. Depicting a word with chips, the child analyzes the properties of sounds, comes up with words with a given sound or according to a given scheme. Such actions prepare him for mastering the rules of grammar and at the same time facilitate the development of reading skills.

According to numerous studies, the ability to read is the basis of academic performance, without it, a student does not assimilate educational material and does not even grasp the meaning of a mathematical problem. Therefore, the speed of reading is taken under control by school leaders.

The oral speech of elementary school students is achieved by enriching phrases and turns of written speech, sometimes in the classroom they repeat the phrases of the textbook verbatim, this gives their speech some unnatural, bookishness, but in this way, they learn the logic of reasoning.

⁵⁴ Архипова, Е.В. Об уроке развития речи в начальной школе № 4 / Е. В. Архипова. – М.: Начальная школа, 2000. – С. 35-39.

The inner speech of schoolchildren reaches significant development, since educational activities require constant self-control. In internal speech, they outline an order, an internal plan of action. Self-report and self-assessment are given in internal speech. And here, too, the influence of the teacher's speech, which determines the order of self-examination, is noticeable.⁵⁵

In general, educational activity significantly accelerates the speech development of children, improves all types of speech.

*Development of thinking*⁵⁶ there are two stages in primary school. At the first stage, visual and effective thinking prevails in children, analysis of material based on visible, perceived features of objects. Training actions are performed according to the sample. Generalizations are made on the basis of visual signs. Even in grammar, the preposition "on" is more easily distinguished if it denotes a specific ratio of objects - a book on the table. It is much more difficult for them to single out the same preposition in an abstract meaning - for memory, the other day.

The educational material on the subjects is presented in the 1st-2nd grade so that the important signs are clearly expressed. The composition of the number is represented in pairs by digits in two windows of a multi-storey building or by two quantities of specific objects: 5 circles and 2 triangles, etc.

The educational process is saturated with visual aids. But on their basis, verbal generalizations are already underway. More often it is a generalization on functional or utilitarian grounds: it is to ride, it is put on, etc. The main criterion of knowledge is the student's ability to come up with his own example.

This level of intelligence is Zh. Piage⁵⁷ called the stage of specific operations. Systematic educational work leads to a change in children's thinking. The second stage in its development is characterized by the assimilation of scientific concepts with their generic relationships and classification. The program of classes is full of requirements and tasks for finding correlations between phenomena or defining concepts with indication of generic features and specific differences: "a noun is a part of speech that ..." and then the specific features are listed.

The judgments of the younger student are based on visual signs of objects. But they are already assimilated on the basis of intellectual activity. So, analyzing the image of a grain field, children express an abstract judgment: "Winter crops are grain plants sown in autumn, for winter."

By the 3rd-4th grade, more and more judgments of schoolchildren reflect the essential connections of phenomena, and visual elements are minimized. The stage of formal operations is being prepared (Zh. Piage).

⁵⁵ Возрастная и педагогическая психология /Под ред. И.О. Климановой. – М.: Педагогика, 1982. 305 с

⁵⁶ Выготский, Л. С. Мышление и речь. Изд. 5, испр. — Издательство 'Лабиринт', М., 1999. — 352 с.

⁵⁷ Жан Пиаже - «Избранные психологические труды» 1994 г.

These features of thinking do not fully express the capabilities of younger schoolchildren. Experimental training organized by D. B. Elkonin ⁵⁸ and V. V. Davydov in Russian schools, shows that already at the beginning of learning, children can explore ways to solve mental problems, build and test hypotheses, build mathematical reasoning in an abstract schematic form like: "If the first is equal to A, and the second is twice as large, then we can find what the second is equal to, and then find their sum."

The development of abstract thinking is already embedded in the very structure of educational activity. It assumes the ability of a student to find a common way of acting in similar educational tasks, that is, the ability to present concrete practical tasks as educational and theoretical.

Making a conclusion in the development of thinking of a younger student, modeling actions have a special role in the development of thinking of schoolchildren, when it is necessary to reproduce the text of the story in abbreviated form, make a presentation plan, briefly write down the condition of the problem or the formula of actions for its solution, express the ratio with letters, signs or a graph.

LITERATURE:

1. Bakieva X "Speech development of younger schoolchildren in Russian language lessons" 2016
2. Arkhipova, E.V. About the lesson of speech development in elementary school No. 4 / E. V. Arkhipova. □ M.: Elementary school, 2000. □ Pp. 35-39.
3. Vygotsky L. S., The dynamics of mental development of a student in connection with learning // Vygotsky L. S. Mental development of children in the learning process. M.; L.: GIZ, 1935. pp. 33 - 52.
4. Age and educational psychology /Edited by I.O. Klimanova. - M.: Pedagogy, 1982. 305 p.
5. Vygotsky, L. S. Thinking and speech. Ed. 5, ispr. – Publishing house "Labyrinth", M., 1999. – 352 p.
6. Jean Piaget - "Selected psychological works" 1994
7. The problem of age periodization in the works of D. B. Elkonin. Accessed: December 10, 2017

⁵⁸ Проблема возрастной периодизации в трудах Д. Б. Эльконина. Дата обращения: 10 декабря 2017.